

Deliverable 2.8

WP2 Annual Report Y4

Workpackage 2

Responsible Partner: 36-INSA, 2-AGES

Contributing partners: 7-SZU, 14-UT, 23-UoS, 25-NUIG, 33-NVI

GENERAL INFORMATION

European Joint Programme full title	Promoting One Health in Europe through joint actions on foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging microbiological hazards
European Joint Programme acronym	One Health EJP
Funding	This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.
Grant Agreement	Grant agreement n° 773830
Start Date	01/01/2018
Duration	60 Months

DOCUMENT MANAGEMENT

Title OHEJP deliverable	Annual report Y4 (WP2)
WP and task	WP2, tasks WP2-T1, WP2-T2, WP2-T3.2, WP2-T4 and WP2-T7
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Due month of the deliverable	M48
Actual submission month	M49
Type <i>R: Document, report DEC: Websites, patent filings, videos, etc.; OTHER</i>	R, DEC, other Save date: 26.01.2022
Dissemination level <i>PU: Public (default) CO: confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services).</i>	PU <i>See updated Grant Agreement</i>
Dissemination <i>Author's suggestion to inform the following possible interested parties.</i>	<p>OHEJP WP 1 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 2 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 3 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>OHEJP WP 4 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 5 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 6 <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>OHEJP WP 7 <input type="checkbox"/> Project Management Team <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Communication Team <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Scientific Steering Board <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>National Stakeholders/Program Owners Committee <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>EFSA <input type="checkbox"/> ECDC <input type="checkbox"/> EEA <input type="checkbox"/> EMA <input type="checkbox"/> FAO <input type="checkbox"/> WHO <input type="checkbox"/> OIE <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Other international stakeholder(s):</p> <p>Social Media:</p> <p>Other recipient(s):</p>

ANNUAL REPORT Y4 (WP2)

Description of the deliverable

The deliverable *D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP2.8* (which in the original project proposal did not exist) consists of a brief summary of WP2 activities performed in the second year of the project (Y4: M37-M48) and was intended to be established jointly with tasks **WP2-T3**, **WP2-T5**, **WP2-T6**, **WP2-T7**, part of which are being realized during Year 5 (M60).

WP2 aims at determining the naturally occurring Antimicrobial Resistance genes (ARG) background load and the microbial biodiversity in the tested environmental compartments.

Briefly, in Year 4 we completed the sampling campaign of WP2. All countries extracted extracellular DNA and total DNA from their collected samples following the laboratory protocols, which were made available in Year 3 by the WP2 leader and deputy. All countries sent a selection of their samples based on DNA quality and concentration criteria to an external company for 16S amplicon sequencing (V1-V9 region) and target enrichment (= antimicrobial profiling). All countries have already obtained summary reports (Excel) for their successfully processed samples for both 16S amplicon sequencing and gene enrichment (= antimicrobial profiling). In addition, the FASTQ files generated in the sequencing process of both the 16S and the target enrichment analysis were made available by the company and is being used by WP2. All FASTQ files will be uploaded by project partners to ENA under a common *umbrella project*.

Analysis of the bacterial diversity is now being performed by the FED-AMR analysis team, which integrates WP2 experts on statistics, bioinformatics and AMR. The raw datasets used are the **16S microbial profiling** reports (Excel files) obtained by the different WP2 partners. The first step of this analysis was the harmonization and integration in the data of several variables. Next we will proceed with Alpha diversity analysis after removing contaminants. This will be followed by filtering the data to remove noise and normalizing which is necessary to make accurate comparisons of microbial abundance between samples by removing the influence of sequencing depth and gene length. It will be followed by differential taxa abundance analysis and ordination analysis. This work will be done using R packages like Phyloseq or Vegan among others. In a second step, we are searching for intra-country and multi-country differences between compartments, subcompartments, time-points or DNA types. Identification of naturally **transformable species** was first piloted in the 16S data obtained from the Austrian samples and now is being extended to all countries.

Regarding the obtained results for identification and quantification of ARG by **target enrichment**, are being now re-analyzed using a previously published protocol by Lanza and coworkers [1]. In addition, the mobilome and heavy metal resistance genes are also under analysis

Samples were also used for direct cultivation, **isolate** characterization by whole genome sequence (**WGS**)-based typing, antimicrobial susceptibility testing (AST). WGS and AST are still in progress but will be completed soon. The WP2 bacterial collection is a diverse set of relevant bacteria (clinically-relevant and also environmental bacteria), from several distinct reservoirs that will overall contribute to understand the dissemination of antimicrobial resistance (AMR) within the compartments, reinforcing the One Health approach.

Results derived from those analysis are now being interpreted through statistical comparisons. The first results from WP2 were already presented as posters at the OHEJP ASM2021 by Austria and by Portugal. See 12M Report for more information and the deliverables from the WP2.

Also, the first manuscript, a genome announcement for an multidrug-resistant (MDR) clone detected in wastewater, was published by Cabal et al (2021). There, was reported the first draft genome sequence and annotation of a MDR extraintestinal *Escherichia coli* sequence type 1193 (ST1193) isolated in a wastewater treatment plant in Austria. This *E. coli* ST1193 is an important source of fluoroquinolone resistance, which has emerged in recent years. [Cabal A, Peischl N, Rab G, Stöger A, Springer B, Sucher J, Allerberger F, Ruppitsch W. 2021. Draft genome sequence of a multidrug-resistant *Escherichia coli* sequence type 1193 pandemic clone isolated from wastewater in Austria. *Microbiol Resour Announc* 10:e00762-21. <https://doi.org/10.1128/MRA.00762-21>].

Other manuscripts will be in preparation soon, as the obtention of results and their analysis were delayed due to the COVID lockdown, during 2020 and 2021.

Associated deliverables

D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP2.5 Shotgun sequencing: ARG diversity in tested environmental compartments (T2.3.1)

Confidentiality of the document

The current deliverable is public.

References

1. Lanza VF, Baquero F, Martínez JL, Ramos-Ruiz R, González-Zorn B, Andreumont A, Sánchez-Valenzuela A, Ehrlich SD, Kennedy S, Ruppé E, van Schaik W, Willems RJ, de la Cruz F, Coque TM. In-depth resistome analysis by targeted metagenomics. *Microbiome*. 2018 Jan 15;6(1):11. doi: 10.1186/s40168-017-0387-y. PMID: 29335005; PMCID: PMC5769438.